

TABLE I

SURVEY INSTRUMENT: QUESTIONS AND DETAILS ADDED TO GUIDE THE RESPONDENTS OF THE ONLINE SURVEY (HOSTED ON SURVEYMONKEY).

Q#	Question	Details added to the prompt
<i>Opening Message (after the study informed consent detailed info)</i>		
		<i>This Survey has 14 questions and is estimated to require 15 minutes (at most) to complete. All questions should be answered from the team's perspective. If you are part of multiple teams, you should submit different responses for each team or ask another team member to respond to this Survey for all of you. Thank you for your collaboration.</i>
<i>Team Profile</i>		
Q1	You and your Team	Note added: <i>We need to know who you are and what team you're filling out this survey for so that we can make sure we're getting a representative set of responses. We will not contact you unless you give us permission below (in Q14), and we will not share your information outside the research team (for more, see the informed consent).</i> Options added to inform in individual text boxes: <i>a. Your name; b. E-mail (work); c. Team's name.</i>
Q2	How many members are in your team?	Note added: <i>(team size)</i> Note added: <i>For "team", let's consider people directly working on the software development project joining retrospective meetings (which can include non-technical members or members across multiple teams).</i>
Q3	How long has it been since someone joined or left your team?	Note added: <i>(total of months or years)</i>
<i>Project and Sprint</i>		
Q4	What is the average or regular sprint duration?	Note added: <i>(Iteration length)</i> Options added to select one: <i>a. 1 week; b. 2 weeks; c. 3 weeks; d. 4 weeks; e. Other, please specify (and indicate the unit of time).</i>
<i>Retrospective Meetings</i>		
Q5	How long has your team been doing retro meetings?	Note added: <i>(total of months or years)</i>
Q6	How important do you think retro meetings are to your teamwork? In respect to (A) how the team works together and (B) the work the team does.	Options added (for each sub-question) to select one: <i>a. Not Important; b. Slightly Important; c. Moderately Important; d. Important; e. Very Important.</i>
Q7	How long do your retro meetings normally take?	Options added to select one: <i>a. 30 minutes; b. 60 minutes; c. Other, please specify (in minutes).</i>
Q8	How often do you have retro meetings?	Options added to select one: <i>a. Every 2 weeks; b. Monthly; c. Other, please specify (and indicate the unit of time).</i>
Q9	In which configuration do you usually conduct retro meetings?	Options added to select one: <i>a. In-Person; b. Remote or Online; c. Hybrid.</i>
Q10	Which tools does your team use during a retro meeting?	Options added to inform in individual text boxes: <i>a. Engineering team metrics & analytics tool (e.g., industry partner tool, in-house dashboard)</i> <i>b. Task management or issue tracking data (e.g., Jira, Linear, Trello, Asana for reports and remembering action items)</i> <i>c. Whiteboards - Physical or Online (e.g., Miro, FigJam, Jamboard)?</i> <i>d. Any others?</i>
<i>Project Data</i>		
Q11	What data does your team usually keep track of?	Note added: <i>For "Data", let's consider project data (e.g., Google Analytics, Mixpanel, Amplitude, Datadog, Sentry, NewRelic, Splunk, etc.) and/or team performance & health and codebase data (e.g., DORA & SPACE metrics, test coverage, issue tracking reports, timesheets, code activity, as a few examples).</i>
Q12	What data does your team usually bring to a retro meeting?	Note added: <i>This is an open-ended (or free-form) question; to complement your answer, you can consider adding:</i> <i>a. Is there a subset of data used while planning a Sprint or during the Sprint?</i> <i>b. What is the source for each of them? How frequently are they reviewed?</i>
Q13	Would you like to share any comment or complementary info for any of the previous questions?	Note added: <i>This is an open-ended (or free-form) question; to complement your answer, you can consider adding:</i> <i>a. What is done during preparation activities? (before start)</i> <i>b. What is done during the meeting?</i>
<i>Closing</i>		
Q14	Would you like to be part of the next phase of this study?	Options added to select one: <i>a. Yes (you will have the chance to confirm your interest later); b. No.</i>

TABLE II
ONLINE SURVEY RESPONSES: 19 TEAMS (T#). Q2-Q4 REGARDING THE TEAM; Q5-Q9 REGARDING RETROSPECTIVE MEETINGS.

T#	[Q2] Team sz	[Q3] Team changes	[Q4] Sprint Duration	[Q5] Retro Since	[Q6-A] Imp. to Team	[Q6-B] Imp. to Work	[Q7] Length	[Q8] Frequency	[Q9] Config.
T01	13	3 mo	2 wk	yrs (unit NA)	VERY imp.	VERY imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T02	15	6 mo	2 wk	3 yrs	Important	Important	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T03	15	2 mo	2 wk	1.3 yrs	VERY imp.	Important	45 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T04	15	1 mo	Kanban	3 yrs	VERY imp.	Important	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T05	16	1 mo	6 wk	2 (unit NA)	Slightly imp.	Slightly imp.	60 min	Every 8 wk	Remote/Online
T06	11	1 mo	No sprint	8 yrs	Slightly imp.	Slightly imp.	60 min	<i>ad hoc</i>	Hybrid
T07	7	3 mo	2 wk	2 yrs	Important	Slightly imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Hybrid
T08	5	4 mo	No sprint	2 yrs	Important	Moderately imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T09	6	4 mo	2 wk	1 yr	Moderately imp.	Slightly imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T10	6	6 mo	2 wk	2.5 yrs	VERY imp.	Moderately imp.	75 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T11	5	1 mo	2 wk	Monthly	VERY imp.	Important	60 min	Monthly	Remote/Online
T12	10	1 mo	2 wk	less 1 yr	Moderately imp.	Moderately imp.	30 min	Every 2 wk	Hybrid
T13	8	3 mo	Kanban	3+ yrs	VERY imp.	VERY imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T14	8	2 wk	1 wk	2 yrs	Important	NOT imp.	45 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T15	7	9 mo	2 wk	5+ yrs	VERY imp.	Moderately imp.	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T16	6	1 mo	2 wk	3 mo	VERY imp.	Important	60 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T17	11	3 mo	2 wk	4 mo (new team)	VERY imp.	Moderately imp.	45 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T18	7	3 mo	2 wk	2+ yrs (since existed)	Important	Important	30 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online
T19	8	3 mo	2 wk	2+ yrs (since existed)	Important	Important	30 min	Every 2 wk	Remote/Online

TABLE III
HOW IMPORTANT RETROSPECTIVE MEETINGS ARE TO TEAMWORK? (Q6)

In respect to	NOT Imp.	Slightly Imp.	Moderately	Important	VERY Imp.
(A) How the team works together	0 (0%)	2 (11%)	2 (11%)	6 (32%)	9 (47%)
(B) The work the team does	1 (5%)	4 (21%)	5 (26%)	7 (37%)	2 (11%)